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Factors Affecting Job Satisfaction in Kasiglahan Village National High School as Perceived by Educational Leaders and Teachers

Albert Joseph G. Ceniza

Abstract: Teachers' job satisfaction can be a determinant of the manifestation and realization of the most significant objective of education sector, the enhanced educational system which can be considered as one of the factors to the performance of teachers as educators. Since a teacher is a role model for the students, job satisfaction and eventually performance of teachers become very vital in the field of education (Chamundeswari, 2013). The to reveal the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction and its possible relationship to their performance using t-test, ANOVA, and correlation through the SPSS. The study revealed that there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on job satisfaction according to their education, positions, and designation on job satisfaction. It may imply that education, position, and designation have little to no effect on the perception of educational leaders and teachers in job satisfaction. The data analysis showed that there is a weak negative correlation between the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction and their performance, as job satisfaction decreases, the level of performance of educational leaders and teachers also decreases. It also signifies that there is no significant statistical correlation between the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction and their performance. The weak negative correlation possibly transpired by chance on the sample and there is insufficient evidence to say that this correlation exists in the entire population.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Educational Leaders, Teachers, Educational Management, Factors affecting Job Satisfaction

1.1 Performance of Teachers

Motowidlo (2003) defines job performance as based on employee behavior and the outcome is vital for organizational success. The performance of teachers mainly depends on the teacher characteristics such as knowledge base, sense of responsibility, and inquisitiveness; the student characteristics such as the opportunity to learn, and academic work; the teaching factors such as lesson structure, and communication; the learning aspects such as involvement and success; and the classroom phenomena such as environment and climate, and organization and management. If the teachers take care of these factors, their performance can be enhanced to the optimum level (Rao and Kumar, 2004). These

factors are crucial for the realization of the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competencies in the teaching and learning process that the teachers must always consider as indicators of their performance in everyday classroom interaction, building good camaraderie with their colleagues, strengthening the partnership with stakeholders for the realization of the educational goals and objectives.

Leigh and Mead (2005) bring about the fact that the quality of teaching has come down gradually world over, demonstrate that the skills of teachers have come down due to outdated preparation on the part of the teacher and stagnant compensation schemes by the management of the educational institution Jain and Verman state that this condition in the recent years for the teacher has led to (1) very few growth opportunities (2) inadequate compensation structure which signifies that the job satisfaction can be a factor on the performance of teachers. This study intends to assess the perception of educational leaders and teachers on their job satisfaction and relate it to the performance of educational leaders and teachers as reflected in their individual performance commitment and review form (IPCRF) of the previous year since employee's performance is a crucial factor in determining the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization in the fulfillment of their mandate. Highly performing individuals will be able to assist the organization to achieve its strategic aims thus sustaining the organization's competitive advantage (Dessler, 2010).

1.2 Job Satisfaction

Satisfaction refers to the contentment level, interpretation, and attitude of an individual towards a certain thing, circumstances, and/or any phenomena they are experiencing. This can be physical, emotional, and perceptual. Job satisfaction is either a global feeling about the job or a related constellation of attitudes about various aspects of facets of the job. The facet approach is used to find out which parts of the job produce satisfaction or dissatisfaction (Jain & Verman, 2014). These aspects can be the impact of work or tasks on the mental state of the individual, incentives, support system of the organization, and internal stakeholders. Job satisfaction can also be seen as an indicator of emotional well-being or psychological health (Begley and Czaika, 1993; Fox, Dwyer, and Ganster, 1993). Edwards, et al. (2008, p 442) refer to job satisfaction as “an evaluative judgment about the degree of pleasure an employee derives from his or her job that consists of both the affective and cognitive components”. Aamodt, (2009) defines job satisfaction as “the attitude an employee has toward his job.” Moser and Galais (2007) highlighted that employee's ability and opportunities aid in improving their satisfaction with the job level. Job satisfaction can be a great indicator of the effectiveness and efficiency of an individual towards particular task and performance in an organization. It also signifies the personal and subjective perception of an individual to the policies, systems, benefits, and appreciation of the organization's leaders that in the end will affect the performance of the employee, the organization to their clientele, internal and external stakeholders.

According to Robbins and Sanghi (2006), “Job satisfaction is a collection of feelings that an individual holds toward his or her job.” The same was contributed by Masud Ibn Rahman et al (2008) “Job satisfaction is defined as a general attitude toward one's job. In this study, job satisfaction as the independent variable will be assessed according to the perception of educational leaders and teachers and then correlated to the performance of teachers as reflected in their individual performance commitment and review form (IPCRF) of the past year.

2.1 Review Of Related Literature

The perception and interpretation of an individual can be a factor in the level of performance and productivity in a particular task or the fulfillment of the organization's mandate.

Beverly A. Perrachione, Vicki J. Rosser, George J. Petersen (2007) say that research on job satisfaction in the field of education has explored both the consequences (outcomes) and antecedents (influences) of teacher satisfaction. based on the research job satisfaction can result in a high level of retention at the same time increase in teachers attaining tenure.

According to the study of Bloch (2009), there is a positive relationship between promotion and job satisfaction. Educational leaders and teachers or educators are highly encouraged and entrusted to perform a task if promotion opportunities are open for them.

According to the study of Mohamed Imran Rasheed (2010) entitled “Motivational Issues for Teachers in Higher Education”, job design, work environment, feedback, recognition, and decision-making participation can be considered factors in the job satisfaction of teachers in higher education. His research is crucial in demanding the attention of higher education authorities in the Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan to assess and evaluate the motivational issues of teachers in the university.

Robbins et al (2006) stated that employee motivation is the “willingness to exert a high level of inspiration to reach organizational goals, conditioned by the effort's ability to satisfy some individual need”. With this information, we can say that the satisfaction or the motivation of an individual within an organization greatly affects his/her contribution to the productivity and performing its mandate to their clientele.

Shamima Tasnim, (2006) in her research entitled “Job Satisfaction of Faculty Members in Private Universities- In the Setting of Bangladesh” revealed that one of the main purposes of a job is to get payment or salary and it is very natural that a considerable amount of salary will bring job satisfaction. In this study also, she stated that universities should pay more attention to motivating and maintaining their human resources to manifest satisfaction among faculty members and to exert all efforts towards the overall excellence of the organization.

According to the study of Pugno & Depedri (2009) job performance is positively correlated with job satisfaction which signifies the possible effect of job satisfaction on performance. Qazim et al (2012) revealed in their study that to have management efficiency the organization must improve the employees' satisfaction which can lead to competitive advantages and able for them to adapt to the organization's changing environment.

In the study of M. D. Pushpakumari(2008), he found that there is a significant impact of job satisfaction to the performance of employees. Satisfied members of the organization have a high level of positive behavior towards their terms of reference. This signifies that satisfied employees are punctual, concerned about the achievement of the goals and objectives, work fast, have fewer errors and mistakes, speak freely, share ideas, are loyal, and committed, follow the organization's rules and regulations; and exert effort to retain the job. Considering this, job satisfaction affects the performance of an individual in an organization.

Ahmed m. Alzaidi conducted a study on the topic of Job satisfaction among secondary school head teachers. The research highlights the complicatedness of the realization of job satisfaction of secondary school head teachers that is indirectly related to the policy and practice. This study reveals the factors that can affect the job satisfaction of school

head teachers in the city of Jeddah.

Heriyati and Ramadhan (2012) conducted a study entitled “The Influence of Employee Satisfaction in Supporting Employee Work Performance” which intends to analyze the influence of employee satisfaction moderated by employee engagement towards employee work performance and retention. They found out that the satisfaction of employees has a remarkable positive influence on the employees’ performance and retention.

In line with this, the researcher intends to seek the factors affecting job satisfaction and its relationship to the performance of educational leaders and teachers to provide a wider perspective regarding the relationship between job satisfaction and performance.

This study seeks to answer the following questions:

What is the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction according to their:

- a. Education
- b. Position
- c. Designation

Is there any significant difference in the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction according to their:

- a. Education
- b. Position
- c. Designation

Is there any significant correlation between the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction and their performance?

2.2 Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference in the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction according to their education, position, and designation.
- There is no significant correlation on the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction and their performance.

3.1 Methodology

Research Design

This descriptive research aims to assess the perception of educational leaders and teachers on the factors affecting job satisfaction and its relationship to performance in Kasiglahan Village National High School through the utilization of an adapted instrument, and the gathered data. The results can be a basis for the formulation of school-level policies, guidelines, and programs to address possible issues regarding job satisfaction and its possible effect on the performance of the members of the organization. This involves statistical treatment such as t-test, ANOVA, and correlation on the mean score on the perception of educational leaders and teachers towards the factors affecting job satisfaction and performance using the IPCRF of educational leaders and teachers.

Participants

The participants of the study are educational leaders and teachers of Kasiglahan Village National High School on a voluntary and non-compulsory basis. There are 89 volunteer educational leaders and teachers who represent all eight (8) academic departments. Teachers will self-assess their perception of the 10 factors that can affect their job satisfaction using a 5-point Likert Scale (1-Not evident to 5-Highly evident).

Instrument

To achieve the objective of this research, the researcher intends to adapt and revised the survey instrument from the works by Susan Herrington, North Tennessee Private Industry Council in Clarksville, Tenn.

The questionnaire is composed of 10 items that can be considered as factors affecting the job satisfaction of an individual within an organization. To assess the perception of educational leaders and teacher, items will be rate though Five (5) point Likert scale and were scored as 5-highly evident, 4-moderately evident, 3-Evident, 2-Barely evident, 1-Not evident.

The mean score per indicator of educational leaders and teachers, in consideration of their education, position, and designation will be analyzed through t-test and ANOVA; it will be also correlated to their performance based on the IPCRF of the respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research tool/instrument was administered on volunteer teachers. The data gathered out of the Likert questionnaire will analyzed through statistical treatment such as t-test, ANOVA, and correlation utilizing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis Tool

The data analysis tool will be mean, t-test, ANOVA, and correlation with the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

4.1 Results and Discussion

Table 1
Perception of Educational Leaders and Teachers on Job Satisfaction according to Education

Job Satisfaction	Education			
	Bachelor's Degree		Master's Degree	
	Numerical Value	Verbal Interpretation	Numerical Value	Verbal Interpretation
1 Promotion in the company	3.923	Evident	4.400	Moderately Evident
2 Tactful discipline	4.218	Moderately Evident	4.400	Moderately Evident
3 Job security	4.603	Moderately Evident	4.700	Moderately Evident
4 Help with personal problems	3.821	Evident	4.200	Moderately Evident
5 Personal loyalty of supervisor	3.792	Evident	3.800	Evident
6 High wages	4.064	Moderately Evident	4.400	Moderately Evident
7 Full appreciation of work being done	4.333	Moderately Evident	4.400	Moderately Evident
8 Good working conditions	4.410	Moderately Evident	4.400	Moderately Evident
9 Feeling of being in on things	3.936	Evident	4.200	Moderately Evident
10 Interesting work	3.936	Moderately Evident	4.500	Moderately Evident

Table 1 shows that teachers with bachelor's and master's degrees have the same perception of moderately evident tactful discipline, job security, high wages, the full appreciation of work being done, good working conditions, and interesting work; and evident personal loyalty to supervisor. However, teachers with master's degrees higher perception of moderately evident promotion in the company, help with personal problems, and feelings of being on things compared to the perception of teachers with bachelor's degrees. It signifies that teachers with higher educational attainment are more satisfied, can see more opportunities in the organization, and can be more independent.

Table 2
 Perception of Educational Leaders and Teachers on Job Satisfaction According to Position

Job Satisfaction	Position					
	Teacher I		Teacher II		Teacher III	
	Numerical Value	Verbal Interpretation	Numerical Value	Verbal Interpretation	Numerical Value	Verbal Interpretation
1 Promotion in the company	3.981	Evident	4.000	Moderately Evident	3.833	Evident
2 Tactful discipline	4.278	Moderately Evident	4.179	Moderately Evident	4.167	Moderately Evident
3 Job security	4.611	Moderately Evident	4.643	Moderately Evident	4.500	Moderately Evident
4 Help with personal problems	3.852	Evident	3.893	Evident	3.833	Evident
5 Personal loyalty of supervisor	3.889	Evident	3.750	Evident	3.333	Evident
6 High wages	4.074	Moderately Evident	4.179	Moderately Evident	4.000	Moderately Evident
7 Full appreciation of work being done	4.241	Moderately Evident	4.536	Moderately Evident	4.333	Moderately Evident
8 Good working conditions	4.463	Moderately Evident	4.357	Moderately Evident	4.167	Moderately Evident
9 Feeling of being in on things	3.981	Evident	3.964	Evident	3.833	Evident
10 Interesting work	4.352	Moderately Evident	4.357	Moderately Evident	4.333	Moderately Evident

Table 2 reveals that teachers have the same perception of moderately evident tactful discipline, job security, high wages, the full appreciation of work being done, good working conditions, and interesting work; evident in help with personal problems, personal loyalty of supervisor, feeling of being in on things regardless their respective positions. This reveals that teachers have a high perception of job satisfaction regardless of their position. Even so, educators in the position of teacher 2 perceived promotion in the company higher than educators in the position of teacher 1 and 3 which means that the perception of teachers in promotion is varied.

Table 3
Perception of Educational Leaders and Teachers on Job Satisfaction according to Designation

Job Satisfaction	Designation			
	Educational Leader		Teacher	
	Numerical Value	Verbal Interpretation	Numerical Value	Verbal Interpretation
1 Promotion in the company	3.905	Evident	4.000	Moderately Evident
2 Tactful discipline	4.095	Moderately Evident	4.284	Moderately Evident
3 Job security	4.667	Moderately Evident	4.597	Moderately Evident
4 Help with personal problems	4.000	Moderately Evident	3.821	Evident
5 Personal loyalty of supervisor	3.952	Evident	3.761	Evident
6 High wages	4.095	Moderately Evident	4.104	Moderately Evident
7 Full appreciation of work being done	4.381	Moderately Evident	4.328	Moderately Evident
8 Good working conditions	4.286	Moderately Evident	4.448	Moderately Evident
9 Feeling of being in on things	3.952	Evident	3.970	Evident
10 Interesting work	4.381	Moderately Evident	4.343	Moderately Evident

Table 3 shows that teachers have the same perception of moderately evident tactful discipline, job security, high wages, full appreciation of work being done, good working conditions, and interesting work; evident in help with personal loyalty of supervisor and feeling of being in on things regardless their respective positions. This reveals that educational leaders and teachers have a high perception of job satisfaction regardless of their designation. However, teachers have a higher perception of moderately evident promotion in the company but a lower perception of evidence on help with personal problems where it can be said that the perception of educational leaders and teachers differs on the promotion and handling personal problems.

Table 4
Significant Difference on the Perception of Educational Leaders and Teachers on Job Satisfaction According to their Education

Group Statistics

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Score	Bachelor's Degree	10	4.1433	.27590	.08725
	Master's Degree	10	4.3400	.23664	.07483

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Score	Equal variances assumed	1.290	.271	-1.711	18	.104	-.19670	.11494	-.43819	.04479
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.711	17.592	.105	-.19670	.11494	-.43859	.04519

Table 4 reveals that based on the analysis of data, the significance or p-value of .104 is greater than the level of significance of .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers with Bachelor's degrees and teachers with Master's degrees on job satisfaction. This signifies that educational attainment might not affect the perception of educational leaders and teachers toward job satisfaction.

Table 5
Significant Difference on the Perception of Educational Leaders and Teachers on Job Satisfaction According to Their Position

Descriptives

Score

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Teacher 1	10	4.1722	.25622	.08102	3.9889	4.3555	3.85	4.61
Teacher 2	10	4.1858	.28863	.09127	3.9793	4.3923	3.75	4.64
Teacher 3	10	4.0332	.34077	.10776	3.7894	4.2770	3.33	4.50
Total	30	4.1304	.29527	.05391	4.0201	4.2407	3.33	4.64

ANOVA

Score

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.143	2	.071	.807	.457
Within Groups	2.386	27	.088		
Total	2.528	29			

Table 5 shows that based on the analysis of data the significance or f-value of .457 is greater than the level of significance of .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on job satisfaction according to their positions on job satisfaction. It may imply that position has little to no effect on the perception of educational leaders and teachers in job satisfaction.

Table 6
Significant Difference on the Perception of Educational Leaders and Teachers on Job Satisfaction According to their Designation

Group Statistics					
	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Score	Educational Leaders	10	4.1714	.24831	.07852
	Teachers	10	4.1656	.27682	.08754

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Score	Equal variances assumed	.270	.610	.049	18	.961	.00580	.11759	-.24126	.25286
	Equal variances not assumed			.049	17.791	.961	.00580	.11759	-.24146	.25306

Table 6 exhibits that based on the analysis of data the significance or p-value of .961 is greater than the level of significance of .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference in the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction according to their designation. It can be said that designation might not affect the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction.

Table 7
Significant Correlation of the Perception of Educational Leaders and Teachers on Job Satisfaction and their Performance

Correlations

		Perception	Performance
Perception	Pearson Correlation	1	-.082
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.447
	N	88	88
Performance	Pearson Correlation	-.082	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.447	
	N	88	88

The r-value of -.082 revealed that there is a very weak negative correlation between the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction and their performance. As job satisfaction decreases, the level of performance of educational leaders and teachers also decreases. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a very weak negative correlation between the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction and their performance. However, the very weak correlation possibly transpired by chance on the sample and there is insufficient evidence to say that this correlation exists in the entire population.

5.1 Conclusions & Recommendation

Regardless of educational attainment, position, and designation, educational leaders and teachers should always have a positive perception of job satisfaction even though there is a very weak negative correlation between the perception of job satisfaction and performance which occurred only by chance, it is also possible that when the perception of educational leaders and teachers decreases, their performance also decreases. The school administrators, key leaders, and teachers can formulate programs, projects, and/or activities (PPAs) that can ensure the high perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction to ensure their enthusiasm and willingness to perform their respective tasks and mandates.

Conduct targeted and purposivetraining and seminars towards job policies, guidelines, programs, projects, and activities of the educational institution and department which can help the educational leaders and teachers to understand their mandate, roles, and responsibilities that can greatly affect their perception of job satisfaction.

Create a policy, guidelines, or program that can help educational leaders and teachers boost and ensure a high level of job satisfaction within the organization leading to an increase in their productivity and performance.

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Instrument

(http://www.nwlink.com/~donclark/leader/want_job.html#sthash.86o3taW7.dpuf.)

